

The Putumayo Indians and the Rubber Boom¹

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Abstract: *This article approaches the Putumayo Indians' memory of the Rubber Boom, in the voice of the Muinane group coming to grips with their painful memories of that violent past, and in the recent initiative of the Colombian government to declare the reconstructed headquarters of the Peruvian Amazon Company in La Chorrera as an 'Estate of Cultural Interest'. This memory is represented by Indians in the double image of the Basket of Darkness, which holds the memories of violence, and the Basket of Life, which holds the seeds of the future looking forward to the growing of new generations and leaving behind the dangerous memories of violence and sorcery of the past.*

Keywords: *Rubber Boom, Muinane Indians, Putumayo, Roger Casement, Casa Arana, Memory*

In the reports, narratives and testimonies of the Casa Arana period in the Putumayo region, Putumayo Indians speak with their bodies executed, mutilated, tortured, raped and exploited by rubber barons, as has been documented in horrifying detail by Casement, Valcárcel, Hardenburg, Saldaña Roca and many others. In all those tales, they are not actual subjects but objects of compassion, fear or observation; noble savages for Casement, treacherous and savage for Robuchon, cannibals to be civilised for Casa Arana, and objects of ethnographic description for Robuchon and Whiffen. In all of these cases Indians do not have voice but are the objects of disputes among Whites. I want to bring Indians' ways of dealing with memory to the foreground and move to the background the usual literature.

Indians nowadays refer to the memories of the rubber boom as belonging to what they call 'Basket of Darkness'. In contrast to that obscure basket of bad memories, they speak of a 'Basket of Life', where the seeds of the future are placed, looking forward to the growing of new generations and leaving behind the dangerous memories of violence and sorcery of the past. I explore below this powerful double image of Indians' memory and think it is fit to parallel Roger Casement's legacy. What does it reveal to the workings of memory and the representation of history? What is the truth to be sought in the past?

I begin by approaching the Putumayo Indians, in the voice of the Muinane group coming to grips with a painful memory and in face of new changes and challenges at the end of the twentieth Century.

The Muinane Indians Healing the Memory of the Rubber Boom

In May 1993, a group of Muinane people were getting ready to set off to visit their ancient territories. They are

the descendants of one of the peoples that were nearly exterminated by the Casa Arana and the Peruvian Amazon Company at the beginning of the twentieth century. The meagre remnants of their formerly numerous population had resettled further north, beyond the edge of what had been their ancestral lands, which remained nearly uninhabited for many decades.

The impact of the rubber industry and the Casa Arana regime on the Putumayo Indians was enormous. The total Indian population was reduced to perhaps less than a tenth between 1900 and 1930, and the surviving ones were forcefully resettled on the Putumayo River and further south. A few managed to escape north or to hide in the forest. Their social, political and ceremonial organization was severely shattered, and their territory was depopulated, as the forest regrew in what had been a densely populated region. In 1908, Thomas Whiffen (1915) calculated 46,000 as the total population of the Putumayo Indians and 2,000 as the population of the Muinane tribe. By 1993, the Muinane census did not reach 150; these were the descendants of the barely 20 Muinane men and women who managed to survive the Casa Arana regime (Echeverri 1997). These rough numbers just serve as an indication of the degree of the catastrophe these peoples endured.

In the 1980s, the Colombian government officially granted the indigenous groups of the region—Witoto, Bora, Muinane, Miraña, Ocaina, Nonuya and Andoque Indians, the descendants of the peoples who were Casa Arana's labour force—the legal property of the territories they now occupy as well as their ancestral lands in the hinterland. This huge expanse of land—about six million hectares—coincides with Julio Cesar Arana's rubber territories. This new Indian reserve was named *Resguardo Predio Putumayo*. The Muinane Council of Elders—formed by the chiefs of the four main clans—decided in the early 1990s that the re-appropriation of the ancestral territories was necessary to reassert their political autonomy, now formally recognised, and to work towards their social reconstruction.

The Muinane elders in 1993 were the children of those who had directly suffered the slavery and slaughter under the Casa Arana regime. They were born after the rubber boom had ceased and only the oldest ones had first-hand knowledge of the places where the ancient people used to live. They grew up looking away from those stories and those places, finding a way of life on the banks of the Caquetá River, trading timber and game with White people and sending their children to the Catholic boarding school. They grew old far from their land and from the horrifying stories their own parents told—and remained disturbingly connected to them.

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The ancestral territory of the Muinane is located at the centre of the *Resguardo Predio Putumayo*. This territory was known to the elders in words and memories, but they had not returned to it since their childhood. In the 1990s times had changed. They had their territories legally titled and a new generation, for whom these stories were distant, had grown up after them. Their children were intelligent and able, had gone to school, and wanted to know. The banks of the Caquetá River, where they had lived for decades and where they had raised their children, was a foreign land where their ancestors used to go to get fish and stones, but not a place they used to live. The rocky outcrops which mark the Caquetá landscape are the lodges of mythological beings, carriers of evil powers. Further south is the 'Land of coolness', the area where the places of the *malocas* (longhouses) of their forbears rested abandoned, the land that had been deprecated and ravaged, and from where they had been expelled and exiled. It was their *territory*, a word in English (or Spanish or Portuguese) that barely translates the meaning of the Muinane concept: it is not just a tract of land that can be mapped or legally titled; this *territory* is the inscription of life and memory on the land—and this life and this memory had remained amputated since the times of Casa Arana, and the events Roger Casement and others denounced and publicised, but that for the Indians had remained unhealed.

The children of Casa Arana were now elders and they needed to recover that life and that memory they had been unwilling to face for decades. The necessary step was to revisit the territory and to face its memories. At that time, I did not fully grasp the meaning of the decision they took to go and visit the old places. They stated that *territory* was the basis of their education, their government, and their social and ritual organization, and that they needed to go there with their children to show them and retrieve the thread of their life.

And then they started off their journey to the ancient land. The group was formed by three elders of three of the surviving clans (Pineapple, Worm and Drum), and nine boys, three of each clan. They headed first to the ancient territory of the Pineapple clan, and Chucho, its elder, led the group. On May 27th 1993, after five days of trekking into the uninhabited forest, they got to the Manioc creek, a small stream on the Cahuinari River basin, not far from where once stood the Casa Arana section of Matanzas, now covered by forest regrowth. It was in Matanzas where Roger Casement met the notorious Armando Normand: '... with a face truly the most repulsive I have ever seen, I think. It was perfectly devilish in its cruelty and evil. I felt as if I were being introduced to a serpent', wrote Casement in his journal (Casement 1997: 256). The Muinane remember Normand as 'Noroba'. Matanzas means literally 'slaughters' or 'massacres' and the atrocities that happened there were exhaustively documented in Judge Carlos Valcárcel's (2004: 259-

289) book and reported by Hardenburg (1912: 23), in Casement's journal (1997: 253-266) and by many others.

For the Muinane, the place of Matanzas is known as 'Hill of the Wild Cacao Tree'. There lived Chucho's granduncle, who had the name of Jeevadeka (Flower of Parrot Pineapple), a chief of the Pineapple clan of the Muinane. The Muinane tell that Jeevadeka died under the hands of Noroba, who hung him from a pole by his ear piercings.

The group camped a few hours away from the old, haunted site. At night, Chucho spoke and the youngsters recorded his speech on a tape recorder. In his speech, Chucho did not address his fellow elders or his sons and nephews; he addressed Jeevadeka. He spoke like this:

We have truly arrived to the place of the ordeals; we arrived to Manioc Creek, to the Hill of the Wild Cacao Creek [Matanzas]. Your grandchildren have arrived for you to meet them; you do not have to mistake them, as if they were other people. Do not be upset, stay calm. Here are your grandchildren. We know nothing about those who killed you, about those who did all those things to you. You are the ones who know. Now we are a new generation, and here are those who were born after me, and I am guiding them. We came here to heal these children. Here is our chief Jeevadeka. We know nothing of what happened to you. So it is. If we knew, we could speak about that. You came to end your life here. I am showing it to your grandchildren. I am heading them together with my brother. So then, do not take us for strangers. We came here to heal ourselves. This is what we are telling you. That is it.

The next day, by noon, they arrived at the place where Matanzas once stood, now covered with forest. There, Chucho spoke again:

Here, grandfather Jeevadeka, you lived and you are. We are your grandchildren and we have arrived. Up to this place we have reached and we are stepping on this spot. Are you there? We have arrived well, in good heart. Here we are; we are the bones of yours. We are coming back, your grandchildren that were born after you. We mourn and remember you, who are here. Then, for that reason, I myself Kigaibo [Sour Pineapple], your grandson, have arrived, together with people of the Drum clan and the Worm clan. We are with these, our young people, for you to meet, and we come in good manner. We come to seek the good words that you have: the word of life, the word of coolness, the word of nurturing. You ought to give us those words. We are cleaning up on top of you.

We thought we were alone, but we are not alone, you are here. That is why we came, we have reached to you. This is what I am telling you.

I was very struck when I helped Chucho's brother, Jorge, to transcribe and translate these recordings upon their return from their trip. Chucho's address to Jeevadeka begins by avoiding any reference to the violent events of the Casa Arana period: 'We know nothing about those who killed you, about those who did all those things to you', he says. Chucho seeks to heal, not to remember, as if invoking the violence of those days may attract danger. He rather focuses straight away to the young people in the party, and takes care that Jeevadeka's wandering spirit will not mistake them for other people. Chucho is well aware that nowadays they all look very much like the Peruvians and Creoles who enslaved and murdered their ancestors. They now wear clothes and boots, carry *machetes* and shotguns, eat salt and 'smell of onions', as they say.

Chucho's way of dealing with the past when addressing Jeevadeka in this point of the territory is profoundly historical precisely in the fact that he avoids remembering. Instead of looking *back* he looks *forward*; not to the dead but to the living—and he addresses Jeevadeka as if he were alive. He acknowledges the past of killings and slavery by avoiding its memory, and he acknowledges the changes that came about afterwards by stating that no matter what they may look like, they are Jeevadeka's grandchildren who come to pay a visit. Chucho's generation had been unable so far to deal with any of this. None of them felt able to go to the old places and cope with the rage, sorcery and powers that were left scattered, unbound and unsolved. They felt ashamed and powerless, unable to re-establish a connection they were painfully aware was necessary to rebuild their life—after so many years.

That power they lacked in shamanism and magical force to deal with the troubling past, they found again, in an unexpected way, in the new generation. These young people, their own children, gave them meaning and strength to face it. Even though these boys have gone to school, have learnt to read and write in Spanish, and do not resemble much those ancient Indians, they are *alive* and they want to know. Instead of reminding them of the crimes committed against their forebears and claiming revenge for them, he rather chooses to forget. He leaves aside the memory of the ordeals and focuses his discourse on what gives life.

And, paradoxically, it is the artefacts of writing that the young people have learnt from the White people that allows for the close of the circle of this operation of the memory. In contrast to the elders, who rely on the oral speech in the Muinane language as their way of recording and giving meaning to their journey, the young ones carry notebooks, pens and colour pencils to keep a written record of it. Their notebooks are written in Spanish, and in contrast to the speeches of their parents which deal with spirits

and masters of the places, the youngsters compose a quite pragmatic and down to earth journal, carefully annotating times, distances, location of places, animals hunted, meals eaten, and avoiding any reference to their parents' concerns. They happily trek through the forest with innocent eyes, filling their notebooks with their observations and, most notably, with colourful drawings of the places they visit. In their notebooks they make most succinct and uneventful notes of their elders' speech, as this one by Chucho's nephew about the night when he uttered the speech transcribed above: 'For dinner, we ate a woolly monkey we had hunted, and after the conversation of the elders we went to sleep', he writes.

In Matanzas they found the remains of a longhouse or *maloca* and many objects, both Indian and non-Indian: pots, tools, weaponry, glass, etc., in a place which the young people titled 'Matanzas' garbage dump'. Further ahead, they found two large holes, where rubber patrons used to burn the people that they had killed. They made drawings of the holes in their notebooks. They knew those places existed, where dead people were dumped and burnt; vegetation has not regrown on those holes, and they were still clearly noticeable.

The two modes of representation—spoken in Muinane by the elders, and written in Spanish by the young ones—are remarkably complementary. When I would ask any of the elders about their journey, he would right away ask for his son's notebook and would exhibit the colour drawings; with this in his hands, he would calmly and happily refer to the events of the trip. It is as if by being captured in writing and drawing, those dangerous facts would now be contained and manageable. On the other hand, the young ones could confidently devote these facts into writing and deftly design their drawings because they felt that any danger that could exist in their journey would be avoided and dodged by virtue of their elders' speech.

One of the reasons for the extreme precaution of these Indians to leave aside the memory of violence is because it was not only the violence of rubber barons against Indians, but also the violence amongst Indians themselves, which exacerbated a pre-existing condition of intertribal warfare.

We tend to represent the Indians as victims of the violent rubber barons. The dispute among Whites is whether those Indians were ferocious cannibals running in the forest who had to be subjected by any means to become an industrious and civilised labour force, as Casa Arana alleged, or whether they were noble and pacific people enslaved and abused by 'an association of vagabonds, the scum of Peru and Colombia', as Casement claimed in his journal (Goodman 2009: 111). In both cases, Indians are represented as a single, unified subject. But, how was it from an Indian perspective?

Certain Indian tribes, and clans and lineages within tribes, profited from the alliance with rubber

barons to wage warfare against other tribes and former enemies. Besides, young boys from several tribes were raised and trained to raid other groups and to act as executioners of the worst crimes. This exacerbation of internal warfare had more devastating and long-lasting effects than the violence of Whites against Indians. Whites or non-Indians would eventually leave the region, but the families and relatives of the murderers and the murdered would stay, and with those the memories of pending revenges.

This is one of the key reasons why a person like Chucho is quite circumspect about not bringing back the memory of those events, potentially very destructive for today's life. What these elders aim to do is the reconstruction of the social tissue that was torn apart.

This way of thinking, speaking and relating to memory is in no way a peculiarity of this group or of this elder. It is shared by all the descendants of the Putumayo Indians. What is at stake here is not the reconstruction of the truth of the events, or the demands of justice against the White people, but the reconstruction of society and the multiplication in the amounts of people. This implies both particular modes of memory and historical consciousness and the construction of new forms of collective identity.

The Basket of Darkness and the Basket of Life

What the literature calls 'The Putumayo Indians' encompasses three linguistic stocks and seven ethnolinguistic groups: the Witoto linguistic family (Witoto, Ocaina and Nonuya), the Bora linguistic family (Bora, Miraña and Muinane), plus a language isolate (Andoque). Although these peoples are linguistically differentiated, they share a number of cultural traits and a common social and ceremonial organization. Today, they designate themselves under the general name of 'People of the Centre'.

This ideology of one People linked by social and ritual exchanges constitutes the basis for a type of ceremonial and political discourse, which emphasises the common traits of the different groups, putting aside ethnic differences and past conflicts. This ceremonial discourse is called *rafue* in the Witoto language. *Rafue* belongs to what is called the Basket of Life. In this basket belongs the ethics of horticultural work, the raising of children, the production of food, the celebration of rituals. The most accomplished expression of this Basket is the Word of tobacco and coca, which the elders use to care for and to nurture human life. Mythological narratives and violent historical memories—including those of the rubber boom—do not have a place in this Basket.

In contrast with this ritual and public discourse of *rafue*, which is instrumental in the construction of the ideology of a unified moral community (People of the Centre), the conceptual guarding of ethnic differences is maintained in other modes of discourse. Ethnic difference brings about the memory of conflicts

from the past—rivalry among clans and tribes, sorcery, cannibalism—and implies dealing with differences in mythological conceptions (territory, hierarchy among tribes and clans).

Secret, ethnic discourse is closely linked to mythology. Mythology, for these groups, keeps the record of the events of cannibal, malignant, murderous, revengeful and raging beings who tried to destroy and pervert the true humanity. These stories are kept in what is called the Basket of Darkness. These stories do not belong to the public, common discourse of *rafue*, but are kept and maintained by each ethnic group and clan as a defence and source of sorcery and evil power. The stories and events of the rubber boom are but one more layer in this plentiful basket. These baskets of darkness should be kept sealed, because they represent the danger of war—they are, as these people say, their 'nuclear arsenals'.

These two Baskets thus represent a moral organization of collective memory, and configure a form of historical consciousness. The Basket of Life refers to their history precisely for the fact of refraining to remember anything from the past, but on the contrary asserting the maintenance and reproduction of life. The Basket of Darkness keeps secret the memories of dangerous past events. The terror of the rubber boom looms so dangerously that it fills to the rim that Basket. Those memories are not forgotten but kept sealed.

There is certainly an unresolved tension and an impending danger in this organization of memory, because there is always the risk that the contents of the Basket of Darkness may be deployed, undermining the collective project of a moral community. Separating what is secret (Basket of Darkness) from what is public (Basket of Life) has become a task in which the elders invest a remarkable amount of time and effort.

This allows us to better understand Chucho's address to Jeevadeka in the haunted site of Matanzas. In such a dangerous place, he is avoiding the content of the Basket of Darkness and he is pointing to the Basket of Life, through the use of two rhetorical devices: the request of the 'good words' from Jeevadeka—that is, the Word of tobacco and coca—and his explicit references to the new generation.

It is as if these two modes of memory move in opposite directions. Mythology and historiographical narratives of violence point in the direction of the past; *rafue*, the Word of tobacco and coca, points in the direction of the future. The memories of the events of the rubber boom are thus left in an apparent oblivion: discarded in the public discourse, secret in the private discourse; and there seems to be no way to represent them or to think about them. This unresolved tension is solved by the new generation, which functions like a mirror—a reflective space that allows them to face the past in an indirect way. This reflective space is configured paradoxically by purely foreign devices: writing, schooling, use of the Spanish language, state recognition, and so forth.

At a micro-sociological scale, we saw how for the group of Muinane elders journeying with their sons and nephews, their young boys' notebooks and drawings operated as a reflective space which allowed them to face the past. Now, we can perhaps also appreciate the same process in a larger sociological scale.

For these People of the Centre, the rubber boom has been a difficult issue to deal with—either in oblivion or in secret. But the scars left on the bodies and the territory need to be read and interpreted. These marks also can turn into mirrors that allow new modes of healing and representing the past. The actual site of the headquarters of Casa Arana in La Chorrera may play that role. This is a remarkable story, which like all things Arana, is made up of deceit and twisted turns.

The headquarters of Arana as a mirror of memory

In 1922, Colombia and Peru signed a border treaty, which ceded Colombia the territories north of the Putumayo River, where Casa Arana had been operating. Arana, and the people of Loreto, vehemently opposed the treaty, which was finally ratified by the two countries in 1927. But Arana was indeed a clever man; in fact, a year before the treaty was signed, Arana secured the legal title to his possessions in Putumayo and he ensured that under the terms of the treaty he would receive compensation in cash from Colombia.

Arana pretended to be paid £2,000,000, but the Colombian government found his amount extortionate. Finally, in 1939, the Banco Agrícola Hipotecario, a Colombian official bank, bought the rights of Arana in the Putumayo for US\$200,000, but only paid \$40,000 at that current time. In 1954, the Colombian government ordered the termination of the Banco Agrícola, and put the newly created Caja de Crédito Agrario Industrial y Minero (Caja Agraria) in charge of its liquidation. In 1984, Caja Agraria ratified the purchase made by Banco Agrícola back in 1939, and paid the heirs of Arana the remaining US\$160,000. In this manner Caja Agraria consolidated the full property of the old Arana possessions in Putumayo, which were called *Predio Putumayo* 'The Putumayo Estate' (Colombia 1989).

Putumayo Indians were totally unaware of all these moves until, in 1985, Caja Agraria decided to make use of its property and designed a huge plan of development for the Predio Putumayo, with the investment of two million dollars in an 800-hectare farm in La Chorrera. Caja Agraria erected its main premises on exactly the same spot where Casa Arana had stationed its headquarters and main rubber depot.² The news came as a shock: Caja Agraria claimed property of the whole Indian Territory on the basis of having purchased it from the heirs of the company that had tortured and enslaved the Indians! 'Those titles are stained with blood', claimed the priest of La Chorrera in numerous letters he sent to Colombian authorities. These Indians began a vehement protest against the

presence of the Caja Agraria and its claims of ownership of the region. The situation gained momentum and an agreement was reached in 1988, when the Colombian government proceeded to constitute the land as a *Resguardo* (Reserve) on April 23 of 1988, in favour of the indigenous groups of the region.

In 1993 the Presidency of Colombia acquired the old Casa Arana house from Caja Agraria to lodge a new Indian secondary school, and the Colombian First Lady travelled to Chorrera for its inauguration. *El Tiempo*, the largest Colombian newspaper, headlined the news: 'Between 1900 and 1910 violence prevailed in Casa Arana. About 40,000 Indians were murdered. Today, after eight decades, the house and its bad memories will become an epicenter of education. Last December 21st, the Indians [...] erased the ghost of that genocide'. ('De casa histórica a salón de clases' [From historic house to classroom], *El Tiempo*, Bogotá, 29 XII 1993)

That was the same year the Muinane set off to visit the old places of the rubber boom. And if the 'ghost' of that genocide has not actually been 'erased', it certainly provides a reflective space for the new generations to represent memory in new ways. It is remarkable that the notorious place, with its dungeons where Indians were kept chained, where dozens of Indians were burned in drunken feasts of horror, now becomes a place for the education of the new generation.

Furthermore, in May 2008, the Colombian Ministry of Culture declared the house as an 'Estate of Cultural Interest Nationally', and the Minister of Culture—Paula Moreno, a Black woman—travelled to La Chorrera to announce the news. On that visit, a 48 year-old Bora Indian commented: 'Casa Arana is like bereavement. The school covers that image we have of the past, and I want that [the government] support it because it gives us solace' ('La Casa Arana, de lugar de muerte a sitio para la cultura indígena' [The Casa Arana, from place of death to site for Indian culture], *El Tiempo*, Bogotá, 24 V 2008). Afterwards a respected female leader remarked: 'We have our hopes placed here. Even though Chorrera does not receive many visitors, we want to refurbish the rooms to function as a hotel in Casa Arana. This may be the opportunity for Chorrera to become a tourist site' (Ministerio de Cultura 2008).

The symbolic act had soothing and encouraging effects—mild ones in any case. For the Bora man, it is the education of children that brings solace, not the fact of the house being declared of 'cultural interest' for the nation. For the woman leader, it is the hope that the house will attract tourists, and with them income for the people; much needed income for raising and educating the children—the house is thought as a patrimony *for the future*, not a memory of the past.

Declaring the rebuilt premises of Casa Arana as an object of public cultural interest for the nation is still an opaque mirror. The well-intentioned or politically convenient reasons of the Ministry of Culture in that

declaration fall short of accomplishing a reappraisal of the events that building evokes—both for the Indians who suffered its direct impact and for the country, Colombia, that gave them its nationality and that was also accomplice and witness to those events.

Indians are still unable to deal with that. The bereavement is long-lasting. For Indian elders, like Chucho, that memory is not to be recalled in order to be able to live on, or is a source of evil power that should be kept in secrecy. The survivors of the catastrophe managed to rebuild a new society over the fragments and pieces of a former social order that was irretrievably lost. It is the philosophy of multiplication, the ethics of horticultural work and the Word of tobacco and coca which guides the moral agenda of this social project. Memory is thus subordinated to the imperative of life. Writing, schooling and the State provide an anchor that perhaps will allow new modes of memory in the younger generations. Even though we still do not hear voices from that generation that make sense of all that in new ways, those devices and institutions—utterly alien to the Indian world—do indeed provide a possibility of reflecting and seeing beyond the muted pain and raging revenge.

The rebuilt headquarters of Arana in La Chorrera now lodge the young men and women descendants of the Indians that saw that same house as a place of exactions and fear. That house-turned-school also holds a library where the books, reports and documents written about that time begin to pile up: translations of Hardenburg's book, of Casement's report, new editions of Valcárcel, and what has been written by Colombian and Peruvian historians. Among the various sources, the name of Roger Casement stands as symbolizing a turning point, as a torch of truth and justice in the middle of the blackest night. Those young boys and girls do not fully understand what it means that he was Irish or why he was hung. No matter his background or circumstances, the sheer truth is that his voyage up to Putumayo one hundred and one years ago did make a difference.

This opaque mirror can perhaps be polished and perfected to be able to shine in full. Like Chucho, I myself do not see, do not understand when looking straight back—I just feel fear, pain and rage. I need to look forward into this new generation, and it is to them we owe true truth and true justice. They are our actual true mirrors of memory.

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Notes

- ¹ This article is an edited version of 'To Heal or to Remember: Indian Memory of the Rubber Boom and Roger Casement's "Basket of Life"', published in *ABEI Journal* (São Paulo, Brazil), Number 12, November 2010, pp. 49-64.
- ² I wrote a piece (Echeverri 2009) about a set of photographs taken on the ruins of the ruins of Casa Arana in Chorrera in 1977.